

**D5.2 - POLICY BRIEF - POLICY PRIORITIES
TO SUPPORT THE SUSTAINABLE TRANSITION AND
EXAMPLES OF GOOD POLICIES**

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and bio-based systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The goal of achieving a net-zero emissions European economy by 2050 demands a shift from linear, fossil-based systems to circular, bio-based systems. This transition is complex and relies on transitions in many fields which need to be supported by new and adapted policies that particularly align with the European Green Deal.

This second policy brief, part of SUSTRACK Task 5.1, discusses new policies and policy changes to support the transition to a Circular Biobased Economy (CBBE). First, a summary is presented of the information derived from a literature review on existing policy instruments and key learnings to be taken into account when aiming for more effective and consistent policy design for transitioning to a more CBBE. Next, the SUSTRACK policy approach used to develop consistent policy sets for supporting the transition towards a CBBE in four main sectors of the economy, namely textiles, plastics, chemicals and construction. This is also illustrated with one policy set example for the plastics sector. At the end of the brief, the main conclusions and recommendations are presented.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION, GOAL AND SCOPE	9
1.1 Introduction	9
1.2 Approach	9
1.3 Structure of this report	10
2. POLICY APPROACHES TO PROMOTE TRANSITION	10
2.1 Policies that promote transitions to a CBBE	10
2.2 Some learnings on policy design for transition to CBBE from resource and environmental economics	12
3. SUSTRACK POLICY APPROACH	13
3.1 Designing consistent policy solutions	14
3.2 Example: Policies for non-packaging plastics	15
4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	18
REFERENCES	20

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 SUSTRACK working definition of the Circular Bio-Based Economy (CBBE)..... 9

Figure 2 Structure of SUSTRACK policy factsheets15

Figure 3 Policy sets for the plastics sector16

List of Abbreviations	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
CBBE	Circular Bio-based economy
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
EEB	European Environmental Bureau
EGD	European Green Deal
EoL	end-of-life
EPR	Environmental Product Responsibility
ESIF	European Structural And Investment Funds
ETS	Emissions Trading System
EU	European Union
GDP	gross domestic product
GHG	greenhouse gas
MSW	Municipal solid waste
NGO	Non-governmental organization
OECD	The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
PC	Polycarbonate
PEF	Polyethylene Furanoate
PLA	Polylactic Acid
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
ROI	return on investment
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SME	small and medium-sized enterprise
SUP	single-use plastic products
SUPD	Single-Use Plastic Directive
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION, GOAL AND SCOPE

1.1 Introduction

The goal of achieving a net-zero emissions European economy by 2050 demands a shift from linear, fossil-based systems to a Circular Bio-Based Economy (CBBE). This transition is complex and relies on changes in many sectors, which need to be supported by new and adapted policies, aligning particularly with the European Green Deal.

This policy brief, part of SUSTRACK T5.1, identifies and discusses the learnings derived from a literature review and presents the SUSTRACK policy approach to identifying consistent policy approaches and priorities for the CBBE.

1.2 Approach

The CBBE is still an abstract and fuzzy concept, not only because it is still in an early stage, but also because many different visions and expectations are reported in the literature. To identify policy options that effectively advance the transition and contribute to CBBE goals, a clear definition of the CBBE was worked out in SUSTRACK. Figure 1 depicts a graphical illustration of the definition.

The definition’s purpose is to structure the various goals and means associated with the CBBE in order to identify leverage points for policymakers to create effective and consistent policies. Basically, the definition describes how the abstract goals and principles of the CBBE can be broken down into “policy means”. These means, such as recycling or using residues, provide a more tangible basis for designing policy instruments than rather vague overarching goals or principles such as sustainable resource management or efficient resource use.

Figure 1 SUSTRACK working definition of the Circular Bio-Based Economy (CBBE)

The policy leverage points (light green segment) most often mentioned in the reviewed literature include cascading use, R' strategies such as recycling and reuse, and the use of resources such as biomass and wastes. These CBBE elements provided the basis to guide and structure the policy review and the SUSTRACK policy approach and recommendations for policy sets.

1.3 Structure of this report

This report has four chapters, including this introductory chapter. In Chapter 2, a summary of the information derived from a literature review on policy instruments and consistent policy design for the transition towards a CBBE is presented. Firstly, it provides a summary of types of policy instruments that are already implemented or recommended to be used to support the transition to a CBBE. Secondly, it presents a couple of key learnings derived from the literature to be taken into account when aiming for more effective and consistent policy design for transitioning to a more CBBE. In Chapter 3, the SUSTRACK policy approach is presented to develop consistent policy sets for supporting the transition towards a CBBE in four main sectors of the economy, namely textiles, plastics, chemicals and construction. The chapter provides a brief overview of the methods and principles used to design the policy sets followed by an example for only one sector, which is the plastics sector. The final chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations.

2 POLICY APPROACHES TO PROMOTE TRANSITION

In SUSTRACK, a literature review was conducted to identify existing and new policy instruments that aim at supporting the transition to a CBBE. This resulted in a database with 107 policy instruments. In addition, a second literature review was done to ensure that selected policy solutions are consistent and effective. Most of the insights derived on this last aspect were derived from resource and environmental economics literature. In the next sections, a summary of the literature review outcomes is provided, typically outlining the state of play of recommended policy instruments to promote transitions to circular and/or biobased practices.

2.1 Policies that promote transitions to a CBBE

Policy instruments that promote the CBBE transition can be grouped into instruments that focus on phasing out fossil resources and instruments that target a sustainable use of other resources.

Firstly, there are policy instruments that stimulate the **phasing out of the fossil resources use** in the economy. These did not necessarily only focus on the sectors addressed in SUSTRACK. The most well-known instrument that is already implemented in the EU but is also applied in other countries or regions outside the EU is the ETS (Emissions Trading System). Currently the EU-ETS is limited to the energy sector, specific emission-intensive manufacturing industries, as well as aircraft operators flying within the EU and departing to Switzerland or the United Kingdom. From 2024, the EU ETS will also cover emissions from maritime transport and building sector. There are also EU plans to examine the possible inclusion of emissions from municipal waste incineration from 2028. In Japan, there is also an ETS, but this country also has several policy instruments that aim to stimulate alternative non-fossil energy sectors such as the hydrogen and nuclear sectors. Similar stimulation instruments were already introduced in the EU in 2003 with the Directive on Biofuels for Transport (2003/30/EC) followed by the RED (I, II, III), the Fit for 55 packages all focused on stimulating renewable energy production and consumption. First, they focused strongly on the introduction of biomass-based energy, but in last decade these instruments also widened

towards other forms of renewable energy sources. They also gradually moved towards setting stricter sustainability criteria on the use of biomass for energy, and lately, there is more attention for competition for the use of biomass in energy, transport and material applications. In addition to ETS and other carbon pricing instruments, the development of national and regional strategies or plans is also widely seen as necessary to guide the EU and the world towards a carbon-neutral future. The EU is now also introducing a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) to price CO₂ emissions for certain imported goods to ensure a level playing field between EU countries and third countries. Very early adopters of a carbon tax system, mostly addressing the fossil energy sectors, were Scandinavian countries and Denmark, which introduced it in the early 1990s.

Secondly, some instruments specifically address **resource use efficiency and circularity**, particularly in the non-energy sectors. One sector for which many policy instruments were designed at the EU, national and local levels is the waste sector. In the beginning, the EU-wide policy approaches focused mostly on improving the management of waste, such as the Waste Framework Directive and the EU Landfill Directive. In EU policy, one can also notice that there has been an attention shift to more prevention of waste production and recycling, and this was most strongly targeting certain sectors, such as plastics and other packaging materials. Recycling quotas for waste are often set in the national and regional laws or only as indicative targets in strategies or action plans. Germany, for example, set strict recycling targets for municipal waste of 50% by 2020, rising to 65% by 2035.

In addition to these general categorisations of policies, the following sector-specific insights emerged.

For the (non-packaging) **plastics sector**, several instruments at the EU and national level were introduced for which some examples are the EU Single-Use Plastics Directive, the EU Plastic Bags Directive, the EU Policy Framework on Biobased, Biodegradable and Compostable Plastics, the EU WEEE Directive for recovery of plastic components in electric and electronic waste and EU regulation on plastic food contact material regulating their composition. An EU directive is also planned to address the use of microplastics in products. Also, more national instruments addressing the plastics sector can be mentioned, such as levies for plastic bags (applicable in most EU countries), refund systems for plastic (PET) bottles, etc.

Furthermore, the **packaging products** have become heavily regulated at the EU level, such as through the EU Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation that promotes reuse, recycling and other forms of recovery of packaging waste. Germany introduced a packaging Law that covers a wide range of instruments. It requires packaging material to be designed from the start so that it can be recycled. Producers of packaging have to participate in waste collection schemes; packaging waste has to be collected separately; producers and retailers have to take back empty packaging. Quota for recycling of 55-90 % (quota depends on type of waste) of collected packaging waste is also set in it.

Instruments stimulating more resource-use efficiency can focus on recycling **resources**. For example, the German Sewage Sludge Ordinance requires reducing the phosphorus content in sewage sludge below 2% and recycling of phosphorus extracted in this process by 2029. In the same category, but then, enhancing circular use of textiles was a VAT reduction measure for textile repair services. Since the **textile sector** is a very large sector and consumption is still strongly growing, it has large challenges including in terms of GHG emissions. This explains why there is an increase in policy instruments specifically targeting this sector and stimulating more circular uses, but also by, for example, discouraging fast fashion and stimulating recycling, reuse, and repair.

Thirdly, several instruments are mentioned seeking to stimulate the **use and market penetration of bio-based products** in different sectors such as in construction. For this, action plans at national and regional levels are proposed, but also measures such as setting quotas for biomaterial use in certain sectors or promoting uptake through public procurement. Another approach seen is a refund system for achieved GHG savings because of use of renewable materials.

Fourthly, instruments were also suggested to **stimulate cascading use**. These included putting (higher) taxes on the use of virgin materials, applying a VAT (Value Added Tax) reduction on secondary material use, and prioritising wood uses for traditional forestry products before it is used for energy generation.

In recent years, more policy instruments are developed that have a **broader approach to circularity and resource efficiency** and that focus on the design and the whole production chain of products. Examples of current instruments at the EU level include the Ecodesign Directive, which is proposed to be extended to more sectors, the EU Ecolabel Regulation, and Extended Producer Responsibility schemes (EPRs). The latter aims to hold manufacturers responsible for the waste generated by their products. By requiring manufacturers to take back and recycle their products, EPR schemes can incentivise them to design more sustainable products and reduce waste.

For detailed information and further inspiration on good example policy instruments collected in the literature review, consult SUSTRACK D5.3 (Chapter 3 and also the separate Annex 1).

2.2 Some learnings on policy design for transition to CBBE from resource and environmental economics

The focus on the environmental and resource economics literature helped SUSTRACK obtain a better understanding of designing effective and consistent policies for transitioning to a CBBE. Basically, the observations from this review can be summarized according to five lessons learned.

- 1) Recycling should not be increased indefinitely due to several reasons. Recycling itself requires resources, which is why excessive recycling can lead to more resource consumption than it saves, including material, financial but also labour resources. Recycling can also cause pollution and socially undesirable effects. Accordingly, it is challenging to determine optimal recycling rates for different products. In SUSTRACK it was, therefore, decided not to recommend the setting of politically defined recycling targets. Instead, it was seen as more effective to focus on policy instruments that change market conditions in a way that efficient levels of recycling emerge and that all trade-offs in the use of resources in recycling are considered.
- 2) As to resource extraction, the rate of efficiency is also difficult to establish since various market failures are involved. For example, environmental externalities from natural resource extraction are not properly reflected in market prices. Government action is needed to ensure that adverse impacts on, for example, climate, water, soil, air and biodiversity are reduced and prevented. In a global economy, this is not an easy task. In SUSTRACK, this aspect led to the conclusion that strong attention should be paid to sustainability risks related to resource extraction and that total use of virgin resources should possibly be limited.
- 3) There is a risk related to the use of subsidies as a policy instrument, even if it targets supposedly sustainable practices such as circularity and use of biomass. This is because

subsidies lower prices, and this may lead to increased resource consumption, and it incentivises faster disposal of goods, and indirectly, it may increase income that can be spent for additional consumption. For the design of effective policies in SUSTRACK, two lessons are drawn: (i) Instead of subsidising a desired product, it may be more efficient (and sustainable) to focus on market failures and correct them, thereby disincentivising undesired products (based on Sorenson, 2017). (ii) In case subsidies are used, they should come with clear sustainability criteria, restrictions on resource use and provisions for resource use efficiency.

- 4) It has been shown that in some markets, like textiles, an increase in circular practices such as recycling and reuse will have a rebound effect in that this also leads to an increase in consumption. A learning for SUSTRACK is, therefore, that policy instruments are also needed to influence consumption behaviour.
- 5) Besides market failures for environmental externalities, there is also a need to take market failures into account related to innovation. The SUSTRACK learning from this is that R&D support to innovation and support for scaling up production quantities should be part of the portfolio of instruments recommended.

For a more detailed description of these learning, including used references, it is recommended to also read SUSTRACK D5.3. The learnings presented here have been taken into account in the SUSTRACK policy approach that is further presented in the next chapter.

3 SUSTRACK POLICY APPROACH

Creating policy solutions for a CCBE is a challenging task. As mentioned in the previous chapter, there is already a high number of regulations - at regional, national and EU level - that are intended to promote the transition. They include recycling quotas, standards for product design, extended producer responsibilities, thresholds for toxic substances, information disclosure requirements and many more. Still, progress in the CBBE transition remains limited. For example, the share of recycled materials in the EU's total material footprint has increased by only 1.1 per cent between 2010 and 2023 (EEA 2025).

Documents such as the EU Bioeconomy Strategy or the EU Circular Economy Action Plan seek to provide guidance to accelerate the transition. Despite these efforts, the future shape of the CBBE is still vague in many respects, for example, in regard to the desired (sustainable) level of biomass use or material recycling in the long run. In addition to such fundamental uncertainties, literature and stakeholders engaged in SUSTRACK have emphasised policy fragmentation and inconsistencies as key obstacles for further progress. The multitude of policies also raises bureaucracy for businesses and governments, while the EU is in urgent need to reduce it to remain competitive (European Commission 2025). It is questionable whether simply adding more policies in the current piecemeal manner will turn the tide.

Against this background, SUSTRACK contributes to identifying consistent policy approaches and priorities for the CBBE. For this purpose, transition barriers, market failures related to biomass use and circularity practices as well as sources of policy inconsistencies were reviewed. The findings were used to combine regulatory solutions, both existing and proposed, into consistent policy sets. The next subsection provides a brief overview of the method, followed by an example for a policy agenda for the plastics sector. Similar policy sets for the construction, textiles and biochemicals sectors were also developed and can be consulted in D5.3.

3.1 Designing consistent policy solutions

The SUSTRACK approach for CBBE policies rests on the following premises, based on a review of relevant literature:

- 1. Avoid CBBE paradoxes:** First, biomass use and circularity are sustainability proxies, i.e., they are concepts that help translate complex sustainability goals into actionable policies (Kirchherr et al. 2017). However, these proxies are imperfect in the sense that they promote sustainability only up to a certain point. Using too much biomass or pushing so-called R'-measures, such as recycling beyond a certain level is likely to negatively impact relevant sustainability goals. For example, expanding wood use can increase greenhouse gas emissions instead of decreasing them. This applies not only to energy uses but also to material applications, for example, in the construction or textiles sector (Hurmekoski et al. 2023; Hu et al. 2025). Another example for such paradox effects is that high levels of recycling risk consuming more resources or causing higher emissions than are saved (Baumol 1977; Sorensen 2017; Tian et al. 2020; Freire-González et al. 2022). The CBBE potentially also suffers from rebound effects, i.e., resource savings in one place being offset by higher resource consumption in other places (Zink and Geyer 2017). Especially approaches that rely on subsidies to promote sustainable products are prone to produce such unwanted side effects (Hoogmartens et al. 2018; Freire-González et al. 2022). Therefore, SUSTRACK combines measures for promoting biomass use and circular practices with policies that help limit those actions to a sustainable level.
- 2. Select the adequate policy type:** Not every policy instrument is suitable for every purpose. Given the scope and complexity of the CBBE transition - a process potentially affecting tens of thousands of products from various sectors -, it is unlikely that the EU's current focus on instruments like recycling quotas, product bans or substance thresholds will be sufficient. Advancing the transition mainly with such direct regulation tools, that cover markets with increasingly detailed prescriptions, risks a highly bureaucratic and inefficient CBBE. Therefore, more flexible policy solutions should be considered, e.g., taxes, subsidies and tradeable permits. Such market-based instruments give producers and consumers more freedom to adjust their decisions to varying market conditions (Tietenberg 1990). However, these instruments are equally unlikely to be suitable for every context. Policy makers should therefore analyse thoroughly which type of policy intervention is adequate for which task in the CBBE transition. To support this decision, SUSTRACK has outlined exemplary policy sets for both policy types - direct regulation and market-based instruments - along with strengths and weaknesses of each approach.
- 3. Create targeted solutions:** The bioeconomy and the circular economy pose distinct policy challenges, despite having many cross-connections. Circularity is important also for non-biobased products, and substituting fossil-based products with biomass may be a sustainable solution even where the bio-based alternative cannot be reused or recycled. In addition to this, both visions - the bioeconomy and the circular economy - face different market failures, at least partially. While the bioeconomy is mainly hampered by climate externalities (van Kooten et al. 1995; Lundgren 2008; Lintunen and Uusivuori 2016; Schindler et al. 2024), the lack of recycling also concerns products that are not associated with high greenhouse gas emissions (Gaudet 2007; Sorensen 2017). Designing effective and consistent policy solutions for the CBBE, therefore requires a mix of instruments specifically addressing the separate challenges. Consequently, SUSTRACK suggests different policy sets, one to promote a sustainable use of biomass and another for advancing circularity.

Figure 2 shows the resulting structure that was applied in SUSTRACK for designing consistent and effective policies for the CBBE transition. Based on a review of existing and proposed policy solutions and discussions with stakeholders, individual policy instruments were selected for each sector analysed in SUSTRACK (textiles, (non-packaging) plastics, chemicals and construction). The following chapter illustrates the results for the plastics sector. It should be noted that the suggested policies are examples and could be replaced by other instruments, provided that these are functionally largely equivalent. For example, instead of an emissions tax, an emissions trading system could be used, or a tax reduction could be replaced by direct subsidy payments.

Figure 2 Structure of SUSTRACK policy factsheets

3.2 Example: Policies for non-packaging plastics

As mentioned above, there are already several legal acts in the EU seeking to align plastic production and use with CBBE goals. The majority of these acts address plastic packaging. This is reflected in the fact that collection and recycling rates of this type of plastic are considerably higher than in the case of non-packaging plastic, even though the latter makes up 60 - 75 % of total plastic demand in the EU (EEA 2022). Therefore, the following policy options focus on the CBBE transition in the non-packaging sector.

Figure 3 provides an overview of possible instruments for the sector. To create a consistent policy agenda, the following steps can be taken, according to the structure outlined above:

1. Selection of adequate policy type: Whether the direct regulation or market-based instruments are more suited for transforming the plastics sector can be decided according to various criteria, such as effectiveness, efficiency, fairness and acceptance, administrative costs, impacts on public budgets, compatibility with legal requirements and other policies. Often, market-based policies are highly effective and can provide substantial efficiency gains at relatively low administrative costs (e.g., Cludius et al. 2019; Eslahi et al. 2026). They should therefore be the default solution, unless there are compelling reasons to use other policies. In the case of plastics, such a reason could be that possibly very high carbon prices far beyond the levels in the EU-ETS would be necessary to be effective (Zibunas et al. 2022; Weerdt 2024). This challenge has been noted also in regard to other industries outside the energy sector (Aidt et al. 2017; Pollitt et al. 2020). Using subsidies for bio-based or recycled plastics, on the other hand, would place a heavy burden on public finances. A substantial use of subsidies also comes with high risks of unintended side effects, including increased waste creation (Sørensen 2018) and decreasing natural carbon sinks (Hu et al. 2025; Philippidis et al. 2023). In addition, stakeholders participating in SUSTRACK events revealed a preference towards direct regulation solutions. Hence, these and other instrument types should lead or at least complement the use of market-based policies in the plastics sector.

Policy Set: Circularity			Policy Set: Biomass		
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments		Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	Quota for use of recycled content for producers of non-packaging plastics (e.g., major waste sources such as cars, electrical devices etc.) Ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products to improve ease of repair, recycling etc. Public procurement	Innovation subsidies for new technologies, practices and products connected to the re-use, repair or recycling (etc.) of non-packaging plastics	Promote transition	Product subsidy paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria	Innovation subsidies for new bioplastics technologies and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support their market penetration
Limit resource use	Product bans of (further) single-use and short-life plastic products or product parts where sustainable and low-cost alternatives incl. reuse and repair are available	Carbon price for use of virgin fossil feedstocks as production input, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics	Limit resource use	Sustainability criteria for receiving the product subsidy. E.g., mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, restriction to durable products etc. Additional: Cap for share or total quantity of biomass in the sector	Carbon price on emissions from low-value biomass uses, e.g. from bioenergy and single-use / non-durable bioplastics products

Figure 3 Policy sets for the plastics sector

2. After selecting the preferred policy type, specific instruments must be selected:

- To promote circularity, literature and existing policies suggest the use of quotas for recycled content in plastics use and ecodesign criteria for products containing non-packaging plastics.
- As these instruments tend to shift the financial and administrative burdens of the transition to producers, they could be balanced with demand side measures, e.g., public procurement of sustainable plastic products.

- c. To promote the bioeconomy, i.e., the switch from fossil to bio-based feedstocks, subsidies could be applied.
- d. To ensure a sustainable resource use in this direct regulation approach, a further increase in plastics consumption and waste may be prevented by extending existing product bans (EU SUP Directive) to other products beyond the packaging domain (single-use or short-life plastic products).
- e. Regarding biomass, creating sustainability criteria for material uses in the sector (similar to those for energy in the EU Renewable Energy Directive) can help to limit total demand to a sustainable level. This can contribute to meeting the climate target in the land use sector (EU LULUCF Regulation), to mitigating climate and biodiversity risks from indirect land-use change (iLUC) or to limit land use for biomass and related trade-offs with food security. The larger the pulling effect from the bioplastics subsidy, the more restrictive the sustainability criteria must be.
- f. A cap on total biomass uses in the plastics sector - via suspending subsidy payments for bioplastics after total biomass use reaches a certain quantity - can support such criteria and provide additional protection from overusing the resource.

Various variations and amendments are conceivable for this policy approach. For example:

- Instead of product bans that can be challenging in a world with thousands of often complex consumer items, putting a carbon price on using fossil feedstocks in the plastics industry may pose a more efficient alternative. While it was mentioned that carbon pricing alone could be of limited effectiveness as a leading instrument, in combination with a quota for recycled content, it could take the role of assisting in limiting plastics demand by driving low-value plastic uses out of markets. The key advantage over a ban is that carbon pricing uses market forces to identify low-value products, whereas bans quickly become outdated in dynamic markets and require complicated political decisions that are prone to rent-seeking (lobbying).
- Carbon pricing could also possibly avoid the need to define elaborate sustainability criteria for supporting material uses of biomass. Theoretically, carbon pricing should cover all biomass emissions to achieve an efficient allocation between natural carbon storage in forests, material biomass uses and bioenergy (Lundgren 2008; Lintunen and Uusivuori 2016).¹ In practical politics, though, low acceptance for such a measure can be expected, as it appears to put the renewable resource biomass on the same level as fossil fuels. For this reason, limiting carbon pricing to selected low-value applications (or exclusion of high-value applications from the carbon price) might constitute a politically feasible variation. This, however, comes at the price of higher complexity in the form of the need to decide which applications have low or high value. These various trade-offs between efficiency, bureaucracy and acceptance should be examined in more detail before using carbon pricing in the plastics sector.
- Innovation subsidies or similar support measures are a low regret option, because they provide alternative solutions for emission- and resource-intensive products. This helps to reduce costs that instruments like quotas, bans or carbon pricing impose on society. Innovation also contributes to ecological sustainability by increasing resource efficiency and to EU competitiveness. Therefore, irrespective of the selected policy approach or specific instruments, this policy should always be considered. It is important to note that innovations do not only refer to research and development, but also to policies

¹ Pricing physical greenhouse gas emissions in the waste sector, e.g., via the EU Emissions Trading System, is likely to be ineffective due to transmission problems. Therefore, pricing carbon embedded in products as proxy for future carbon emissions (upstream pricing of feedstock use) could provide an alternative.

that support market penetration and scaling up new technologies (for further details, see SUSTRACK D5.5).

- To support sustainable biomass use and limit the administrative costs associated with sustainability criteria, priority areas could be designated where (additional) biomass cultivation does not conflict with other sustainability targets (e.g., biodiversity conservation) (see also SUSTRACK D5.5).

A comprehensive description of this policy set as well as policies for the sectors textiles, chemicals and construction, can be found in SUSTRACK D5.3.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

The review presented in this policy brief provided us with a number of key insights and learnings that need to be taken into account for designing more effective and consistent policy instruments to guide the transition to a more CBBE.

Firstly, the review showed that policy instruments aimed at supporting the transition to a more CBBE can be grouped into instruments that help phase out fossil resource use and those that address resource use efficiency and circularity. Secondly, the review of policy instruments provided several sector-specific insights on challenges that are most important but also most challenging to tackle. For the packaging, textiles and plastics sectors, many EU and national policy instruments were introduced in recent years to address the high fossil resource use, the lack of biodegradability and compostability, the challenge of microplastics loss to the environment, over consumption, and the lack of market penetration of renewable biobased products. Thirdly, policy development for circularity and resource efficiency requires policy instruments that address both the design and the whole production chain of products.

There were five important learnings derived from the design of policy instruments for transitioning to a CBBE: Firstly, excessive recycling can lead to more resource consumption than it saves, including material, financial, but also labour resources. Secondly, resource extraction efficiency is often overrated because environmental externalities from natural resource extraction are not properly reflected in market prices, and more government action is needed to ensure these adverse impacts. Thirdly, there is a risk related to the use of subsidies because they generally lower prices, and this may lead to increased resource consumption, which may incentivise faster disposal of goods and indirectly, it may increase income that can be spent for additional consumption. Fourthly, an increase in circular practices such as recycling and reuse also goes together with a rebound effect in that this also leads to an increase in consumption. Fifthly, innovation support should also target the scaling up of production chains to prevent market failures

Recommendations

- Circularity and the bioeconomy should be addressed with separate policies to improve policy effectiveness and consistency.
- Given the scope and complexity of the CBBE transition, the type of policy intervention should be selected carefully. Potentials of market-based instruments to manage complexity and reduce bureaucracy should be identified and exploited, provided the cost of environmental externalities is sufficiently and completely covered.

- Policy makers should intensify their efforts to identify paradoxes (trade-offs, rebound, and other unintended side-effects) of the CBBE transition. Current strategy documents, such as the EU Bioeconomy Strategy, do not sufficiently account for these challenges.
- Using subsidies to promote sustainable products not only burdens public finances but also risks unintended side-effects and overall inefficiency. If subsidies are applied, it should be ensured that they are accompanied by clear sustainability criteria and restrictions on resource use and resource use efficiency.
- To ensure that circular practices and biomass use are sustainable, effective measures that limit resource use must be implemented.
- Promoting innovations, including their scaling up, is a low-regret alternative to product subsidies, similar to support for renewable energies. The level of such support should reflect innovation prospects (future cost reduction potentials), not the share of biomass or secondary materials.
- Distributional effects and costs of policies should be considered to improve acceptance and global competitiveness. For example, policy mixes should combine demand- and supply-side measures to distribute the costs of the transition between producers, consumers and governments. Complementing policy approaches with taxes or emissions trading systems can provide financial means for other measures.
- The designation of priority areas for the cultivation of biomass can support the availability of sustainable feedstocks without compromising other sustainability goals. Instead, they can help to create win-win solutions with other policy targets, for example, for improving soil health, biodiversity and other foundations for ecosystem services.

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